

1 **Supplementary Information:**

2 **Seventy-five Years of Systematic Biology: Looking Back, Moving Forward**

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12 **Overview**

13 Datasets, code, and output we produced for this paper are hosted on GitHub:

14 <https://github.com/mlandis/systbiol75>. Files are also archived on DataDryad:

15 <https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.905qfttz8>. Code is written in Python and shared as an interactive
16 Jupyter notebook.

17 **Dataset**

18 We built a table containing 5,150 published records from *Systematic Zoology* (SZ) and
19 *Systematic Biology* (SB). This table was last updated in June 2025, so it does not include all
20 records that will appear in Volume 74 (2025), and it includes no records for Volume 75 (2026).
21 Volumes 1 – 40 for SZ correspond to years 1952-1991, and Volumes 41 – 74 for SB correspond

22 to years 1992-2025. Volumes 1 – 49 each generally contain 4 Issues, whereas Volumes 50 – 74
23 each have 6 Issues.

24 We built our dataset in several stages, beginning with a table provided by Andy Seagram
25 at Oxford University Press, kindly arranged by Bob Thomson and Chris Simon. This table was
26 generated in May 2025 from Dimensions AI (<https://www.dimensions.ai/>) database records and
27 contained information for 4,655 records associated with *SZ* and *SB* between 1952 and 2025. The
28 Dimensions table included five important fields of interest to us (article title, publication year,
29 volume, issue, and DOI) that were almost perfectly complete and consistently formatted,
30 making them suitable for statistical analysis. Three other fields of interest (article abstract,
31 article type, and citation count) were variously incomplete, inconsistently formatted, and/or
32 inaccurate, which each required different correction strategies to amend.

33 First, the article abstracts presented two kinds of problems. Among research articles,
34 293 of 2,757 records in the Dimensions table lacked entries for the abstract field. Initially, we
35 thought this was a defect with the Dimensions table, but it appears that almost no articles
36 before 1967 contained Abstract sections. Among research articles published in 1967 and
37 onwards, 203 research articles lacked text in the abstract field. Because the content of research
38 articles from early volumes of *SZ* and *SB* were only available online
39 (<https://academic.oup.com/sysbio/issue>) as documents (.pdf) that must be individually
40 downloaded and manually processed, we could not extract abstract information for large
41 numbers of documents automatically. We decided not to update the abstracts for these articles.
42 A second issue is that most abstract fields for articles associated with (approximately) Volumes
43 18 – 31 also include the article title, authors, and publication information, which could

44 potentially cause dissimilar papers to appear spuriously similar due to shared metadata. For this
45 reason, we removed these extraneous metadata from all abstracts.

46 Second, the original table contained different citation counts from Clarivate (through
47 Web of Science) and Dimensions AI, but many of these records lacked citation counts or vastly
48 undercounted the numbers of citations reported by Google Scholar (e.g., 10 versus 1,000
49 citations in some cases). Because Google Scholar does not allow bulk retrieval of article citation,
50 we used PublishOrPerish (Harzing, 2007) to generate citation counts for all articles associated
51 with *SZ* and *SB* in 10-year batches. We used ISSN 0039-7989 for *SZ* and ISSN 1063-5157 for *SB* to
52 minimize the chance that our search collected articles from other sources that had a partial
53 match with the journal name. In cases when Google Scholar associated multiple records with a
54 single article, we only retained the record with the highest number of citations. We used article
55 titles to cross-reference the datasets and add Google Scholar citation counts to our main table,
56 and manually updated the citations for any records that had no obvious match. Google Scholar
57 data were collected in June 2025.

58 Lastly, article type fields were often imprecise or inaccurate. The Dimensions dataset
59 only classified articles using generic groups (e.g., articles, book reviews, editorials) and not the
60 custom types used by *SZ* and *SB* (e.g., research articles, points of view, spotlight articles,
61 symposium articles, etc.). However, articles hosted on the *SB* website were correctly sorted into
62 sections that matched the custom types we desired. We wrote a Python script to scrape each
63 article's type along with its title, abstract, DOI, page count, and other relevant information from
64 all issues of *SZ* and *SB* that were hosted on the *SB* website. This netted 5,095 scraped articles in
65 total. We then updated the article types in our main table by matching DOIs and/or titles

66 between the tables. Our new dataset scraped from the *SB* website contained 496 articles not
67 contained in our main table, which we added and populated manually.

68 As part of building this dataset, we also skimmed through the entire dataset several
69 times to check for general correctness. In cases when we noticed individual records or fields
70 that seemed incorrect, we updated them either by visiting the *SB* website, Google Scholar, or
71 downloading the article in question. After including all verified journal articles, removing
72 duplicate entries, and resolving inaccurate article types, our new table contained 5,150 articles
73 with 2,531 research articles, 964 points of view, 326 book reviews, and 1,329 other
74 miscellaneous articles (e.g., announcements, spotlight articles, symposia articles, etc.).
75 Although we believe this table represents the most accurate record of *SZ* and *SB* articles in
76 current existence, we have no doubt that it still contains undetected errors and missing
77 entries/fields.

78 **Analyses**

79 *Article similarity through time.* We measured the similarity among 2,531 research
80 articles published across different volumes of *SZ* and *SB*. To do so, we concatenated the titles
81 and (when present) abstracts of our articles, then passed those strings (the texts) into a pre-
82 trained sentence transformer, SPECTER (Cohan et al., 2020) to embed each article into a 784-
83 dimensional vector space. SPECTER was trained using the titles and abstracts of roughly 146,000
84 scientific articles from Semantic Scholar (Ammar et al., 2018), making it well-suited our
85 purposes. Using the embedded coordinates for the articles, we then computed the mean cosine
86 similarity between all pairs of articles in each pair of volumes. We chose cosine similarity
87 because it only measures the degree to which two embedded vectors are aligned, but ignores

88 the magnitude of the similarity, which could be influenced by the fact that some texts only
89 contained a title (e.g., before 1964) whereas others contained a title and abstract. A cosine
90 similarity score of 0 means the embeddings are orthogonal in vector space and a score of 1
91 means the directions of the embedded vectors are identical. We then plotted the similarity
92 scores as a heatmap (Figure 1 in main text).

93 To assess whether any changes in similarity among *SZ* and *SB* articles through time was
94 of statistical interest, we compared the scores in our main dataset (*D1*) described above to
95 scores for three alternative datasets (*D2 – D4*). We first constructed an alternative dataset (*D2*)
96 from the same *SZ* and *SB* research articles as in *D1*, except we shuffled the publication years
97 among volumes, allowing us to test whether it also induced apparent shifts in similarity. We
98 then generated two more datasets by randomly sampling 20 research articles from the SciDocs
99 dataset used to train SPECTER for each publication year during 1970 – 2019 (SciDocs contained
100 too few records outside of these dates). The first of these two datasets (*D3*) retained the
101 original publication years, whereas the second dataset (*D4*) shuffled publication years among
102 articles (as above). These datasets allowed us to assess the background levels of similarity
103 among all research articles, regardless of discipline, with and without temporal information. For
104 all four datasets (*D1 – D4*), we generated similarity score heatmaps analogous to Figure 1 and
105 plotted the within-year similarity score across all four datasets to aid comparison. Only *D1*
106 demonstrates a clear pattern of increased similarity among articles over time, both for the
107 heatmap of between-year similarities (Supp. Fig. S1) and the line plot of within-year similarities
108 (Supp. Fig. S2). We interpret these results as support for increased similarity among *SZ/SB*

109 research articles published near 1970 and 1990; these increases are not easily explained as
110 random noise or caused by academia-wide changes in writing style.

111 *Topic modeling.* We used BERTopic (Grootendorst, 2022) to predict interpretable topics
112 for our embedded texts. BERTopic takes a set of embedded texts, clusters the embedded texts
113 by similarity, and then associates all clusters with representative keywords to construct human-
114 interpretable topics. The number of topics, the exact topic keywords, and assignments of texts
115 to topics are treated as unknowns to be learned from the texts by the analysis.

116 BERTopic has six main steps: embedding, dimension reduction, clustering, vectorizing,
117 keyword discovery, and representation. The first three steps (embedding, dimension reduction,
118 and clustering) determine which articles are assigned to which clusters. The last three steps
119 (vectorization, keyword discovery, representation) determine exactly which keywords are used
120 to represent each cluster. We used the same text embeddings that were generated for Figure 1.
121 For dimension reduction, we used UMAP with Euclidean distances, a neighborhood size of 20,
122 and a minimum distance to reduce dimensionality to represent our embeddings with 5
123 components. Clustering used HBDSscan with Euclidean distances, minimum cluster sizes of 15
124 and minimum sample sizes of 3, using the excess of mass (eom) criterion for cluster selection.
125 For vectorization, we used a standard count vectorizer to convert the texts into tables of n-gram
126 frequencies (1 to 3 words) while removing common English stop words. Keyword discovery then
127 used categorical Term-Frequency Inverse-Document-Frequency (c-TF-IDF) to find sets of
128 keywords that were relatively unique to each topic, while providing a list of 132 terms from
129 systematic biology as suggested seed words for topics with an up-weighting factor of 2, and
130 using the Okapi BM25 ranking function to boost the importance of rare terms. To improve the

131 final representation of keywords for each topic, we used both the Maximum Marginal Relevance
132 model with a diversity score of 0.3 (mild diversity enhancement) and the Parts of Speech (POS)
133 model from spaCy with the *en_core_web_lg* trained pipeline to eliminate different grammatical
134 forms of the same word (e.g., fish vs. fishes). Lastly, we used built-in tools from BERTopic to
135 construct a topic hierarchy, using 1 minus the cosine similarity for the distance metric. These
136 settings were chosen based on best practices recommended by the BERTopic documentation,
137 familiarity with the dataset, and trial-and-error.

138 Our analysis resulted in 1,799 texts being assigned to 39 topics with high probability. We
139 inspected the summary of topics and representative texts to validate the topic predictions were
140 sensible. Next, we considered the 732 texts that were left uncategorized. We assigned each of
141 these texts to the topic with the highest probability, while leaving alone texts with >0.99
142 probability of being uncategorized. This resulted in all 2,531 texts being assigned predicted
143 topics. Figure S3 displays the topic assignments of all research articles in a two-dimensional
144 space. The “topics_info.csv” and “texts_info.csv” files provide information on topics, topic
145 keywords, research articles (texts), and topic assignments. We used these files to assess the
146 topic assignment quality.

147 We visualized the hierarchical topic scheme using modified versions of BERTopic plotting
148 tools (Figure S4). We then extracted the subtopics associated with the three deepest clusters
149 (“clades”) of topics. For this analysis, the first cluster (top) generally contained topics with
150 keywords associated with classification, nomenclature, and phenetics. The second cluster
151 (middle) primarily contained topics associated with specific clades, organismal traits, or
152 genomic analysis. The third cluster (bottom) contained topics with keywords concerning

153 phylogenetic methods and/or concepts, along with a group of topics regarding the use of
154 phylogenomic models in plants. The representative papers of topics associated with
155 phylogenomics in plants in Cluster 3 have titles such as “Mitochondrial Phylogenomics Of Early
156 Land Plants: Mitigating the Effects of Saturation, Compositional Heterogeneity, and Codon-
157 Usage Bias” (Topic 27) and “A Universal Probe Set for Targeted Sequencing of 353 Nuclear Genes
158 from any Flowering Plant Designed Using K-medoids Clustering”, and have abstracts that place
159 far more stress on methodological innovations over the organismal research. For these reasons,
160 we associate the first cluster with traditional concepts in systematics, the second cluster with
161 “clade biology”, and the third cluster with “phylogenetic biology” (see main text for discussion
162 of “clade biology” and “phylogenetic biology”).

163 We stress that while the topic names were generated by the pipeline and can be
164 considered as results from data analysis, the cluster names were assigned by us (the authors)
165 and should be considered interpretations. It may be that the predicted topics, the clusters, and
166 our interpretation of the clusters (i.e., as representing “clade biology” and “phylogenetic
167 biology”) are all meaningless. To consider this possibility, we inspected all predicted topics, their
168 keywords, the titles of their most-representative articles, and several random articles associated
169 with each topic to gauge whether the prediction was reasonable. We additionally reviewed
170 which topics were associated with which clusters. We judged that the topics within each cluster
171 seemed more similar with each other than with topics from other clusters, and that the topics
172 and most-representative articles associated with each cluster were reasonably accurate (i.e.,
173 there was far more signal than noise).

174 We performed two analytical tests to determine whether the topic prediction pipeline
175 was prone to producing meaningless topics and clustering schemes. First, we measured the
176 proportion of “multi-topic” articles that were associated with probability >0.05 in each of two or
177 more topics, and where the second-best topic received at least half as much support as the first-
178 best topic. We identified 965 (38.1%) “multi-topic” articles in our dataset, of which 885 (35.0%)
179 were associated with only one cluster and the remaining 80 (3.2%) were associated with
180 different clusters. This is expected, since the clusters correspond to the deeper, hierarchical
181 signal in similarity among topics. Second, we generated a dataset of topic-free research articles,
182 where each article was represented by one random abstract and 5-6 random sentences
183 sampled (with replacement) from the original *SZ/SB* research articles; that is, no article was
184 expected to have a cohesive topic. We then re-ran the topic prediction pipeline and found that
185 2,502 of 2,531 (98.8%) of the randomly constructed articles were placed into one of two topics,
186 with both topics falling into a single cluster. This suggests that randomly generated *SZ/SB*
187 research articles fail to produce meaningful numbers of topics or clustering hierarchies, unlike
188 what we obtain from the actual dataset.

189 To visualize topics through time (Figure 2 in main text), we collected the counts of
190 articles associated with each of the three main clusters and each topic for each year. Because
191 the number of articles within a topic could fluctuate radically from year to year, we used a 5-
192 year rolling average for article counts to make the plot easier to read and interpret. Whereas
193 Figure 2 separates the visualization of topic dynamics through time by cluster membership,
194 Supplemental Figure S5 displays all topics together, ignoring the clustering scheme.

195 We note that BERTopic is a stochastic method with a wide variety of tuning parameters.
196 The exact composition of predicted topics, their keywords, and their hierarchy can be somewhat
197 sensitive to analysis settings. However, in general, our experimentation with topic modeling
198 typically led to three main clusters, each composed by similar topics as presented in Figure S4.

199 *Article types through time.* We summarized article types through time in two ways
200 (Figure 3 in main text), as the number of articles per type and the mean lengths of articles per
201 type for each year. We did not perform any statistical tests for this visualization.

202 *Citations by type through time.* We explored whether articles associated with the “clade
203 biology” or “phylogenetic biology” clusters had different citation patterns. Articles concerning
204 “clade biology” tend to be of greatest interest to other experts working on the group, and
205 potentially suffer from lower citation rates due to being overspecialized, taxonomically
206 speaking. On the other hand, an excellent “clade biology” study can become the emblem of an
207 evolutionary process and/or provide an ideal dataset for secondary analyses. That said, many
208 “phylogenetic biology” articles describe new models, techniques, or software that become
209 immensely popular in the field, while others can be exceedingly technical or abstract and have
210 no apparent relevance to practicing biologists. Of all these options, we assumed that extremely
211 popular software packages associated with “phylogenetic biology” would lead to higher mean
212 citation rates when compared to “clade biology”. To account for the fact that older articles
213 generally have had longer periods of opportunity to accumulate citations, we compared articles
214 on the basis of citations per year, computed as the number of total citations divided by the
215 publication age (time since publication + 1). In addition, because articles published within the

216 past 20 years tend to have a higher citation rate than older articles, we limited our comparison
217 to the period of 2000 through 2024 (Supp. Fig. S6).

218 Recent research articles associated with the “phylogenetic biology” cluster indeed tend
219 to be more highly cited (mean=16.4) than “clade biology” articles (mean=12.6), with papers
220 associated with “traditional systematics” being cited the least often (mean=8.2; Supp. Fig. S7).
221 However, “clade biology” papers have lower variability in citation rates (sd=18.4) than
222 “phylogenetic biology” articles (sd=64.3). When using median citation rates, which are less
223 sensitive to extreme values, “clade biology” papers (median=8.7) instead appear to be cited
224 more often than “phylogenetic biology” papers (median=6.9). The most highly cited
225 “phylogenetic biology” papers (99th quantile=139.9) tend to be cited more than twice as often
226 as those from “clade biology” (99th quantile=59.1). Our interpretation is that while a few
227 “phylogenetic biology” articles, particularly software methods, may “strike it rich” and become
228 widely cited, “clade biology” and “phylogenetic biology” papers are cited at similar rates, on
229 average.

230 Reflections

231 David Hull performed a variety of bibliometric analyses in *Science as a Process* (Hull
232 1988) by individually and manually processing the articles available at that time. This included
233 classifying papers into various categories (e.g., “Pro-Phenetics versus Anti-Phenetics”) based on
234 article content. Newer automated language processing techniques, such as those we used in
235 this study, could broaden and complement the original work of Hull (1988).

236 A practical challenge is that automated language analysis requires that the data are
237 complete, consistently formatted, and accurate. Producing a dataset with these qualities was

238 more challenging than we had originally anticipated for several reasons. First, information about
239 the journal itself is scattered across several proprietary and/or private databases. Second, many
240 records in those databases are inaccurate and/or in conflict, making it difficult to know what
241 records can be trusted. Lastly, because the journal itself has changed substantially over time
242 (e.g., in terms of journal name, article types, article formatting, and management), it is difficult
243 to draw comparisons across volumes even if the content is accurate.

244 The Society of Systematic Biologists (SSB) should consider maintaining its own table for
245 all articles published in *SZ* and *SB*. Oxford appears to have some ability to improve the quality of
246 records it provides us. However, ultimately, we think that curating data for the ideal table will
247 require a combination of automated and manual data processing. SSB Legacy Committee Chair,
248 Prof. Chris Simon, raised the idea that we (the authors) gather a team to help with this work.
249 While we did not have enough time to recruit and train others, it seems like an excellent idea
250 for the future to ensure that SSB has an accurate and handy record of what articles have
251 appeared in its flagship journal as well as for the *Bulletin of the Society of Systematic Biologists*.

252 For anyone who has read this far, we encourage you to download the table of *Systematic*
253 *Zoology* and *Systematic Biology* articles and take the time to witness and appreciate the
254 extraordinary diversity of research our community has produced these past 75 years!

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269 **Supplementary Figure S1.** Mean similarity among research articles between different publication years for the
 270 *Systematic Zoology* and *Systematic Biology* dataset with correct (D1) and shuffled (D2) publication years (1952-
 271 2024), and for the subsampled SciDocs dataset with correct (D3) and shuffled (D4) publication years (1970-2019).
 272 Similarity scores may range from 0 to 1. Note, the results for D1 are identical to those presented in Figure 1 of the
 273 main text, except the color scale was altered to aid comparison, given the lower similarity scores generated by D3
 274 and D4. See Supplement text for details.

275

276 **Supplementary Figure S2.** Mean similarity among research articles within each publication year for the *Systematic*
 277 *Zoology* and *Systematic Biology* dataset with correct (D1) and shuffled (D2) publication years (1952-2024), and for
 278 the subsampled SciDocs dataset with correct (D3) and shuffled (D4) publication years (1970-2019). Similarity scores
 279 may range from 0 to 1. The plotted similarity scores correspond to the diagonal cells of the heatmaps presented in
 280 Supplementary Figure S1. See Supplement text for details.

281
 282 **Supplementary Figure S3. Systematic Zoology/Biology** research articles and topics. BERTopic associated 2,531
 283 SPECTER-embedded research articles (points) with 39 inferred topics (colors), represented here in two dimensions
 284 using UMAP. See Supplement text for details.

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288 **Supplementary Figure S4.** Hierarchy of *Systematic Zoology/Biology* research article topics inferred by BERTopic.

289 Cluster 1 (orange, top) generally contains topics associated with classification, nomenclature, and phenetics.

290 Cluster 2 (red, middle) generally contains topics associated with organismal research (“clade biology”). Cluster 3

291 (blue, bottom) generally contains topics associated with models, methods, and phylogenomic approaches

292 (“phylogenetic biology”). These main clusters are also used in Figure 1 of the main text and Supplementary Figures

S6 and S7. Distances are measured as $(1 - \text{cosine similarity})$. See Supplement text for details.

293

294 **Supplementary Figure S5.** Numbers of research articles per topic published in *Systematic Biology* during 1952 -
 295 2025. BERTopic topic prediction divided articles into 39 topics (colors). Article counts were smoothed with a 5-year
 296 moving average to improve readability. See main text and supplementary methods for full details. Supplementary
 297 Figure S3 displays all topics. Figure 1 in the main text shows the trajectories of topics for each cluster represented
 298 in Supplementary Figure S4. See Supplement text for details.

299
 300 **Supplementary Figure S6.** Citation rates through time for research article topic-clusters. Cluster 1 (gold, upper left)
 301 generally contains topics associated with classification, nomenclature, and phenetics. Cluster 2 (red, upper right)
 302 generally contains topics associated with organismal research (“clade biology”). Cluster 3 (blue, bottom left)
 303 generally contains topics associated with models, methods, and phylogenomic approaches (“phylogenetic
 304 biology”). All articles are displayed in the lower right. Articles with citation rates lower than 0.001 were rounded up
 305 to that value. See Supplement text for details.

306
 307 **Supplementary Figure S7.** Citation rates for research articles published during 2000-2024 per topic-cluster. Citation
 308 rate is computed as total number of citations divided by article age. Cluster 1 (gold, top) generally contains topics
 309 associated with classification, nomenclature, and phenetics. Cluster 2 (red, middle) generally contains topics
 310 associated with organismal research (“clade biology”). Cluster 3 (blue, bottom) generally contains topics associated
 311 with models, methods, and phylogenomic approaches (“phylogenetic biology”). Citation rate densities are
 312 accompanied by means (open squares), medians (filled circles), and 1% and 99% quantiles (horizontal bars).
 313 Articles with citation rates less than 0.01 citations/year not shown. See Supplement text for details.

314

315 **Supplementary Figure S8.** Word cloud from the Society of Systematic Biologists home page that is referenced in
316 the main text. The original caption for the image reads: “*Word Cloud from 2024 Members Meeting when*
317 *participants were asked, ‘What attribute do you believe distinguishes systematic biologists from other evolutionary*
318 *biologists?’*”. Image copied October 19, 2025.